

Photocatalytic removal of antacid histamine H₂-receptor antagonist Ranitidine

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Abstract : In the present study photocatalytic degradation of an antacid histamine H₂-receptor antagonist Ranitidine with TiO₂ as photocatalyst under UV irradiation in aqueous solution has been investigated. The efficiency of degradation was optimized by several parameters such as effect of initial concentration, catalyst loading, pH, temperature, irradiation time and addition of H₂O₂ as a co-oxidant. On optimization of various parameters it was found that almost complete degradation of Ranitidine by TiO₂ could be achieved within 70 min for an initial concentration of 0.20 mg/mL of the drug and at a catalyst loading of 0.06 g/L. Study on the effect of electron acceptors reveals that both decolourisation and degradation increase in the presence of the electron acceptor. The maximum degradation efficiency of Ranitidine was achieved with the combination of UV + H₂O₂ + TiO₂ and the optimum concentration of the H₂O₂ is 0.003 mM. The decolourisation and degradation kinetics was found to follow first-order kinetics according to the Langmuir-Hinshelwood (L-H) model. The activated energy for the photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine is 21.28 kJ/mol. Over all photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine by TiO₂ is an effective, economic and faster mode of removing Ranitidine from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Photocatalytic degradation, Ranitidine, kinetic study, TiO₂, UV, H₂O₂.

Introduction

The problem of pollution of the environment with pharmaceutical substances has become a major problem of great environmental concern and receiving much attention as potential environmental pollutants now a days. Pharmaceuticals comprise all drugs, diagnostics and other pollutants. Pharmaceutical substances and personal care products are an emerging class of aquatic contaminants that have been increasingly detected in ground and surface water¹⁻⁹. Residues of pharmaceuticals and their metabolites can be expected in the environment everywhere in the world where humans use drugs. The sources of contamination include pharmaceutical production plants, hospitals, landfills, sewage effluents etc.^{10,11}. It has been estimated that up to half of the pharmaceutical wastewater produced worldwide is released without any treatment¹². A number of studies also found pharmaceuticals in drinking water¹³⁻¹⁵. Several solutions are proposed in this regard, including adsorption¹⁶, chemical oxidation¹⁷, biological¹⁸ and catalytic wet air oxidation (CWAO)¹⁹ etc. The main

drawback of these techniques relates to the disposal of the spent contaminated activated sludges, the control of the appropriate reaction conditions, low efficiencies and operation only within a narrow pH range²⁰. During the past decade, great interest has been focused on a promising technology based on the oxidation of the hazardous and refractory organic compounds, by the use of advanced oxidation processes (AOPs)²¹ in which hydroxyl radicals are generated in order to degrade organic pollutants²². Advanced oxidation processes allow the complete oxidation of organic species. Various combinations of hydrogen peroxide, ozone, and ultraviolet light are used to generate hydroxyl radicals (HO•) in the AOPs. Hydroxyl radicals are the principal agents responsible for the oxidation of numerous aqueous organic contaminants and are quite energy intensive. One emerging technology, however, utilizes illuminated semiconductors and is commonly referred to as the heterogeneous photocatalysis. Various noble metals and their metal oxides (Cu, Mn, Co, Cr, V, Ti, Bi and Zn) have traditionally been used as het-

erogeneous catalysts²³. Ideal photocatalysts should have^{24,25}: (i) photoactivity; (ii) biological and chemical inertness; (iii) stability towards photocorrosion; (iv) suitability towards visible or near UV light; (v) low cost and (vi) lack of toxicity. TiO₂ is known as an excellent photocatalyst. Aqueous suspension of TiO₂ has been used to degrade many organic pollutants²⁶⁻³¹, such as pharmaceuticals^{32,33}, dyes³⁴⁻³⁶, halogenated compounds^{37,38}, pesticides^{39,40}, surfactants⁴¹, oily water⁴² and heterocyclic compounds^{43,44}.

In this communication effectiveness of TiO₂ in the photodegradation of Ranitidine has been studied. Ranitidine (*N*-(2-[[5-dimethylamino-methyl]-2-furanyl]-methylthioethyl) is a histamine H₂-receptor antagonist that works by decreasing the amount of acid released by cells of the stomach^{45,46}. It is extensively used in the treatment of duodenal and gastric ulceration, reflux oesophagitis and dyspepsia^{47,48}.

Results and discussion

Preliminary experiments were conducted to evaluate the feasibility of photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine, to establish experimental conditions for degradation and to analyze the results of the photodegradation experiments in the batch photoreactor. Experiments were carried out to study the main factors involved in the overall performance of the photoreactor: (a) photodegradation of the drug in absence of TiO₂ but in presence of O₂ and UV light; (b) photodegradation of the drug in presence of O₂ and TiO₂ but in absence of UV light; (c) photodegradation of the drug in presence UV light and TiO₂, but in absence of O₂ and (d) photodegradation of the drug in presence of all the above parameters viz. UV light, O₂ and TiO₂.

Best results were observed in that condition when small amount of TiO₂ was added to the solution in the presence of O₂ and UV light (Fig. 1).

Optimization of catalyst concentration :

The effect of photocatalyst concentration on the degradation of Ranitidine was studied employing different concentrations of TiO₂ in the range of 0.02 g/L to 0.1 g/L (Fig. 2). It can be observed that the initial degradation increases proportionally to catalyst con-

Fig. 1. Photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine (a) in presence of viz. UV light, O₂ and TiO₂, (b) in presence of O₂ and TiO₂ but in absence of UV light, (C) in absence of TiO₂ but in presence of O₂ and UV light and (d) in presence UV light and TiO₂, but in absence of O₂, concentration of Ranitidine 0.20 mg/mL at pH 2.5 and temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

Fig. 2. Variation of rate constant with different concentrations of TiO₂ at pH 2.5 and temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

centration up to 0.06 g/L and after that degradation rate of Ranitidine became constant. It was observed that the degradation rate was found to increase with the increase in catalyst. Higher reaction rate at a higher amount of catalyst loading may be explained in terms of complete utilization of incident photons striking on the catalyst surface and/or availability of active sites at the surface.

Effect of initial Ranitidine concentrations :

In order to determine the effect of Ranitidine concentration on degradation of Ranitidine studied were

carried out at different concentrations (0.05 to 0.35 mg/mL) of Ranitidine. The influence of Ranitidine concentration on the photocatalytic degradation has been depicted in Fig. 3. As the concentration increases, the degradation efficiency increases. The possible reason is that, as the initial concentration of the drug increased, more drug molecules are adsorbed onto the surface of titanium dioxide. But the adsorbed drug molecules are

Fig. 3. Variation of rate constant with different concentration of Ranitidine at TiO₂ concentration 0.06 g/L, pH 2.5, temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

not degraded after an optimum dose because the intensity of the light and the catalyst amount is constant. At a concentration of 0.20 mg/mL, 88% of the Ranitidine is degraded by photocatalysis, while at higher initial concentrations not more than 55% of the initial amount is degraded in 70 min. Also with an increase in the drug concentration, the concentration of unadsorbed drug in the solution increases leading to lesser penetration of light through the solution on to the surface of titanium dioxide thereby decreasing the degradation efficiency.

Effect of pH :

It is very difficult to elucidate the effect of pH on photodegradation activity due to the many possible reaction mechanisms; among them, the following three are predominant⁴⁹ :

The water molecules react with positive hole and pro-

duce OH[•]

(i) Hydroxyl radical attack :

(ii) Oxidation by the positive hole :

At low pH, positive holes are considered as the major oxidizing species, while at neutral and high pH, hydroxyl radicals are considered to be the major one. So, the influence of the pH on photocatalytic activity is dependent on substrate type and properties of TiO₂ surface. Ranitidine is more stable in acidic media than in alkaline media therefore Ranitidine degradation was studied at different pH values ranging from 2.5 to 7.9. The degradation was above in 70 min at acidic conditions. As pH increase, the more negatively charged catalysis would induce the electrostatic repulsion between the drug anion and catalyst surface which is unfavourable to Ranitidine degradation. Results show that pH 2.5 is optimum at which maximum degradation of Ranitidine occurs (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Variation of rate constant with different pH at concentration 0.20 mg/mL, temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Effect of H₂O₂ concentration :

The electron/hole recombination is one of the main drawbacks in the application of TiO₂ photocatalysis as it causes waste of energy. In the absence of suitable electron acceptor or donor, recombination step is predominant and thus it limits the quantum yield. There-

fore, it is crucial to prevent electron hole recombination to ensure efficient photocatalysis. Molecular oxygen is generally used as an electron acceptor in heterogeneous photocatalytic reactions. Addition of external oxidant/electron acceptors into a semiconductor suspension has been shown to improve the photocatalytic degradation of organic contaminants by removing the electron hole recombination by accepting the conduction band electron; increasing the hydroxyl radical concentration and oxidation rate of intermediate compound; and generating more radicals and other oxidizing species to accelerate the degradation efficiency of intermediate compounds^{50,51}. Several investigators have investigated the effect of addition of electron acceptors such as H₂O₂, KBrO₃ and K₂S₂O₈ on the photocatalytic degradation of various contaminants^{52–54}. These electron acceptors enhance the formation of hydroxyl radicals as well as inhibit electron/hole pair recombination. In all cases the addition of oxidants has resulted in higher pollutant degradation rates compared to the molecular oxygen. In the present investigation H₂O₂ has been used as an electron acceptor. H₂O₂ increase the degradation rate of Ranitidine by removing the surface-trapped electrons, thereby lowering the electron-hole recombination rate and increasing the efficiency of hole utilization for reactions. With the addition of H₂O₂, the enhancement of degradation is due to the increase in the hydroxyl radical concentration as shown in eqs. (6) and (7).

The effect of addition of H₂O₂ on the degradation of Ranitidine was investigated by varying it from 0.001 mM to 0.006 mM (Fig. 5). It was observed that low concentration of H₂O₂ had a less effect on the degradation of Ranitidine, however with increase in concentration of H₂O₂ the percentage of degradation increased. Satisfactory rate of degradation occur in the presence of 0.003 mM of H₂O₂.

Photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine experiments with H₂O₂ were carried out in three different experimental conditions, viz. in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂ but absence of air, in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and air, and in presence of H₂O₂ only. The better results are

Fig. 5(a). Variation of rate constant with different concentrations of H₂O₂ at Ranitidine conc. 0.20 mg/mL and temperature 30 ± 1 °C.

Fig. 5(b). Photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine (a) in presence of H₂O₂ only, (b) in presence of H₂O₂ and TiO₂, (c) in presence of H₂O₂, TiO₂ and O₂.

obtained in presence of H₂O₂ in comparison to other experimental conditions which are shown in Fig. 5b.

Effect of temperature :

Ranitidine degradation was also studied as a function of the reaction temperature otherwise under the same operating conditions. Results concerning the dependence of the rate constant *k* of the photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine at different temperatures, in the range 293–323 K, are shown in Fig. 6. With increasing temperature, an increase of the apparent reaction rate constant *k* was observed until 45 °C. Higher temperature provides increased TiO₂ electron transfers in valance bond to higher energy levels and hence

Fig. 6. Effect of temperature on the photocatalytic degradation of Ranitidine at concentration 0.20 mg/mL, dosage 0.06 g/L and pH 2.5.

facilitating the electron-hole production that could be utilized in initiating oxidation.

Effect of irradiation time :

The catalyst irradiation time was varied from 10 min to 90 min by taking 100 mL of 0.20 mg/mL Ranitidine solution under the UV light source by loading supported photocatalyst. The results show that photodegradation efficiency increased with respect to irradiation time of photocatalyst (Fig. 7). This reveals the formation of intermediates and its competitiveness with parent drug molecules in the photocatalytic degradation process. The slow kinetics of degradation af-

Fig. 7. Effect of irradiation time on the photocatalytic degradation efficiency of Ranitidine at concentration 0.20 mg/mL.

ter certain time limit is due to the difficulty in converting of present atom ions or slow reaction of OH[•] radicals. Highest degradation efficiency occurred when the irradiation of photocatalyst was continued upto 70 min under the same experimental condition and the removal efficiency of the Ranitidine reached upto 88%.

Langmuir isotherm :

The Langmuir isotherm assumes that the surface of any adsorbent material contains a fixed number of active sites and saturation of these active sites stops the adsorption of the adsorbate. This indicates that the adsorption occurs until a monolayer of adsorption is completed and after completion of adsorption no more interaction between the adsorbent and adsorbate molecules takes place⁵⁵. The Langmuir isotherm is expressed as :

$$1/q_e = 1/Q^{\circ} + 1bQ^{\circ}C_e \quad (8)$$

where q_e is the amount adsorbed (mol/g) and C_e is the equilibrium concentration of the adsorbate (mol/L). Q° and b are the Langmuir constants related to maximum adsorption capacity and energy of adsorption, respectively. When $1/q_e$ is plotted against $1/C_e$, a straight line is obtained (Fig. 8) which shows that the degradation of Ranitidine follows Langmuir isotherm.

Fig. 8. Langmuir isotherm on TiO₂ at concentration 0.20 mg/mL and temperature 30 ± 0.1 °C.

Experimental

Instrumentation :

All experiments of photocatalytic degradation were conducted in a photocatalytic reactor of 150 mL ca-

capacity having a 6W UV lamp. The lamp placed inside the well of quartz glass photo reactor and it emits predominantly UV radiation of 10 mW/cm² at wavelength of 254 nm. The reactor set up was covered with a dark black colour wooden box to prevent UV radiation leakage. For all the pH measurements Decibel DB 1011 digital pH meter was used. A spectrophotometer (Systronic spectrophotometer 166, India) with a 1.0 cm light path quartz cells was used for all photodegradation analysis.

Reagents and chemicals :

The drug Ranitidine (Scheme 1) procured from Cadila Pharmaceuticals Ltd., India, with brand name Aciloc. Anatase form of titanium dioxide with a 325 mesh, 99+ % was obtained from Sigma Aldrich and used as such without further purification. The stock solution of Ranitidine was prepared by dissolving 300 mg of Ranitidine in 50 mL of distilled water and 1 mL of concentrated HCl solution and than 5 mL of 1% PDAB solution is added, after that the solution is heated till 80 °C. A red coloured solution is obtained. Working solution of 0.20 mg/mL was prepared from the stock solution with distilled water. Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.5 to 12.0 were prepared by reported method⁵⁶. All the reagents used were of analytical reagent grade and double distilled water was used throughout the investigation.

Scheme 1. Structure of Ranitidine.

Photocatalytic degradation and evaluation :

For irradiation experiment, 100 mL working solution of the drug of desired concentration was taken into the photoreactor and required amount of photocatalyst was added. The solution was irradiated and bubbled with oxygen, to ensure thorough mixing of the TiO₂ catalyst from the side of the reactor continuously throughout the reaction. A suitable aliquot of

the drug was withdrawn after a specific time interval so that its loss of the drug due to degradation can be taken into account spectrophotometrically at λ_{\max} 470 nm after centrifugation. All photocatalytic experiments were carried out at the pH 2.5 and the reaction temperature was kept constant at 30 ± 0.1 °C.

The efficiency of degradation of Ranitidine can be calculated by using the eq. (9) :

$$E (\%) = C_0 - C/C_0 \times 100 \quad (9)$$

where C_0 represents the initial concentration of Ranitidine and C is the concentration of Ranitidine at time t . E value indicates a higher efficiency of degradation of Ranitidine onto the TiO₂.

Conclusion

In this study, an in-depth analysis on the photodegradation kinetics of Ranitidine was performed. The influences of catalyst concentration, initial pH, drug concentration, electron acceptor, temperature, and irradiation time on the degradation rate of Ranitidine were investigated. The observations of these investigations clearly demonstrate the importance of choosing the optimum degradation parameters to obtain high degradation rate, which is essential for any practical application of photocatalytic oxidation processes. Conclusively, an optimum condition for photocatalytic reactor operation with initial Ranitidine concentration of 0.20 mg/mL was achieved as follows : pH 2.5, catalyst concentration 0.06 g/L, and electron acceptor 0.003 mM. The addition of electron acceptor enhanced the degradation rate of the Ranitidine by 88%. The results of these studies clearly indicate that TiO₂ can efficiently catalyse the photodegradation of the Ranitidine in the presence of UV light and oxygen. Results indicated that it can be applied for the treatment of wastewater contaminated by different pharmaceuticals and organic pollutants.

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